

WILLINGNESS TO PAY FOR AGROFORESTRY BASED TECHNIQUES AS FOOD SECURITY OPTION FOR SMALLHOLDER OIL PALM FARMERS IN EDO STATE, NIGERIA.

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Abstract: The continuous decline in output of the monoculture oil palm production occupying vast land thereby affecting the production of other economic crops emanated the integration of agroforestry practices with based techniques option hence the study. This study was to examining the socioeconomic characteristics of the farmers and determining their willingness to pay for the agroforestry based techniques. Information were sourced with a well-structured questionnaire that formed the data. Multi-stage sampling technique was employed to obtain a random sample size of 250 respondents used for the analysis. Data were analyzed with the descriptive statistics and probit model. The result showed that 75.8% of the farmers were above 41 years of age, 60% female, 81.4% mostly primary education with 82.4% of 15 years of experience and 82% of them planted between 1-4 hectares while the probit result indicated that higher educational level at 1%, farming experience, management practices, sources of food and aesthetic at 5% each with annual income, crop types, logging of trees at 10% each significantly influenced and the likelihood for smallholder oil palm farmers willingness to pay for agroforestry based techniques. The study recommends the regular practice as it is another stream of income since oil palm monoculture is no longer enough for the teaming population in constant supply of food and raw materials. The study suggests the continuous practice of agroforestry based techniques as it enhances productivity, profitability and ecosystem sustainability still attends to the challenges in biodiversity conservation, climate change adaptation and mitigation and food secure.

Keywords: Willingness, agroforestry based techniques, food security and smallholder oil palm farmers.

Introduction:

Agroforestry is an old system of practice by smallholder oil palm farmers in their cropping / farming system termed Intercropping / interplanting / interfarming system. It is a land management system that combines trees and shrubs with crops and/or livestock, either simultaneously or sequentially, to enhance productivity and sustainability. Agroforestry is a forest management practice that involves the deliberate integration of trees and shrubs with agricultural crops or livestock. Agroforestry is a new concept of old practice according to IUFRO, (2004). This has been an option for smallholder oil palm farmers in their farming system as majority of them uphold it because of the immense benefits derived from it as it enhances productivity, increases income,

ecosystem sustainability, ensure food security and increases the living standard of the farmers. Also, it addresses the pertinent weather issues like the biodiversity conservation, climate change adaptation and mitigation (Susanti et al., 2019; Van Noordwijk et al., 2023; Roghan, et. al., 2024). However, as the pressure of the teaming population increases with the high demand in food and raw materials for industries, the monoculture oil palm plantations was no longer sufficient enough to satisfy the current quest for food, raw materials and nutrition insecurity without a sustainable integration of the oil palm with agroforestry practices by these farmers.

Smallholder oil palm farmers in their agroforestry option in Nigeria as multiple enterprise resulting from scarcity of land to optimizes labour utilization, improve equity and benefit - sharing, sustain upland management, increase productivity and increase short term returns (IUFRO, 2004) from the integration of arable food crops and animals to sustain the family needs by making food available, accessible, stabilized and utilized and have excess for sale. This satisfies the four pillars of food security to achieve its stated objectives hence the study. This was among the reasons Nigeria was among the highest food producers before the invention of crude oil that relegated agriculture to the door step. This is evident in the findings of Abolagba Kaine, Onyekwere & Abolagba (2010) that Nigeria produced above 15 percent of the world cocoa and the second largest producer of crop in the world. He further opined that Nigeria ranked high in production of crops as; groundnut, cocoa, beans, palm produce and palm oil. These items were produced by smallholder farmers who are about 40% in Nigeria and 80% of palm oil producers globally in conjunction with other crops, planting between 1-5 hectares in Nigeria (Solidaridad, 2020) that aggregates to the GDP of the economy. Having known agroforestry as a common practice by most farmers and despite their contributions to the overall food production they have not taking cognizance of enormous benefits of agroforestry based techniques with efficient management techniques to improve yield for maximum output. This is not easily adhered to nor practiced let alone adopted by most smallholder oil palm farmers and the willingness to pay for the practices by most of them is a mirage. Most farmers find it difficult to adopt the needs as it attracts extra technical know-how and more cost of labour despite the significant impact on their output. The willingness to pay a certain amount to practice this is affected by a lot of factors as opined by Amaechina and Eboh, (2006) on the factors affecting the willingness to pay for agro-forestry. The factors hindered the versatile increase in food and raw material production from oil palm monoculture sector leading to low food production and food shortage by these farmers. The various agroforestry based techniques were discovered, outlined, practiced and adopted by experts in the research institutes for maximum, sustained and enhanced output that are environmental friendly. They are;

Alley Cropping system was developed in IITA in 1970s to manage the fragile low activity soil in humid and sub-humid zones of the sub-saharan Africa. It is the growing of trees in rows or other configuration while growing crops between the tree rows (Owa, et al., 2006; Okere, et al., 2015). It is the technique that involves planting food crops especially leguminous crops in alleys between rows of shrubs/trees that requires pruning during cropping to avoid excessive shedding and competition. It is a cropping and fallow phase that happens

concurrently for a better yield and sustainable soil improvement. This is in line with Ugbah et al., (2009) and Daizy, et al.,(2008) that the oil palm spacing in alley of 9mx16m and 9mx20m have been recommended for continuous intercropping with food crops as fresh fruit bunch yields per hectare were better at these spacing.

Taungya farming is a temporal agroforestry system that combines the production of tree crops and arable crops on forest land cultivated between rows of young forest trees during the establishment year (IITA, 2000). This is the most common practice done in oil palm plantations as arable crops are planted within the first 4 years before oil palm fruiting and before canopy closes to avoid competition and shading leading to low output (Owa, et al., 2006; Omorefe, 2016). This allows for a short term returns from arable crops for family sustenance both on and off season.

Multi-purpose tree crop land is a based technique of deliberately leaving / planting desirable economic trees on the farm during land preparations where the density of natural tree is low. This helps to retain trees with low desirable traits (Owa, et al., 2006).

Shifting cultivation and Bush fallow is among the oldest based practices of agroforestry option that involves the continuous destruction of bushes through cutting and burning of natural forest depending on their cycle (Salami, 1992). This allows tree fallow for some years for canopy to close before cutting to enrich the soil and clear the surface for arable crop production.

Snailing is a based technique of rearing snail which is among the minute livestock that has recently been integrated into farming system in agroforestry option that stood out among Nigerian farmers as an after effect of the alert sounded by FAO on the insufficiency of protein intake derived from animals among Nigerian citizens (Adesope, 2000). Snail farming should be encouraged and integrated into agroforestry option as a new subdivision of sustainable animal production (Adewale and Kafayat, 2022). Snail rearing has various benefits which include the following: it is economical to manage the housing types, healthcare and feeding system in snail production; it has high adaptability to various sorts of geographical predicaments (can be reared in urban or rural areas); they are profoundly reproductive; they are proficient meat producers; they have high health restorative worth – they have prophylactic and curative functions for certain diseases such as hypertension (Adewale and Kafayat, 2022). Snails are commonly fed on diets of tree crops and arable crops such as shed tree leaves, fruits of pawpaw, pineapple, banana, pear, egg shells, oil palm leaves, watermelon and leaves of cassava, pumpkin, pawpaw, cocoyam, and water leaf, cassava peels, melon, maize amongst others. It is a prolific venture with short term rate of return on investment. Agbogidi et al., (2008) opined that snail contains a relatively high amount of protein and iron and a low amount of fat as a good nutritional value.

Apiculture is another agroforestry based technique of Bee keeping in Apiaries for the production of honey and wax. This is done by planting of some specialized woody trees for their nectar producing flowers and pollen cherished by bees to boost honey production and borrow in their holes for shelter of their colony (Owa., 2006). For instance, trees like *Acacia* spp, and *Pentaclethra macrophylla* (Salami, 1992).

Aquaforestry is agroforestry option based technique that connects trees with aquaculture to provide fodder when falling leaves in the ponds decompose as fertilizer to herbivorous fishes and modify their natural habitat,

provision of firewood for fish processing, provide adequate microclimate for the pond in the provision of shade and shelter from direct sun light.

Despite the aforementioned agroforestry option based techniques, due to dearth of information on the technicalities involved in the based techniques which the farmers lack and unable to harness, this study tends to establish a relationship to know if they are willing to pay for the based techniques to enhance sustainable practices as to increase output. This was done by examining their socioeconomic characteristics and estimating their willingness to pay for the based techniques.

Methodology:

The study was conducted in Edo State located in southern Nigeria which was created in 1991 from the then Bendel State with its capital in Benin City. The State comprises eighteen local government areas with three Agro-ecological zones; Edo North, Edo Central and Edo South (Edo State Agricultural Development Programme (EADP) (2018). It has an estimated population of 4,777,000 in 2021 and ranked the 20th most populous state (5,250,000) in Nigeria as at 2024 (Nigerian Census Data, 2021) with a population density of 170/km² (ESPS, 2023). The State lies between longitude 05° 35^l E and 05° 44^lE and latitude 06° 44^lN and 06° 21^lN (Cirella, Iyalomhe and Adekola, 2019) with boundaries; Delta State in the south, Ondo State to the west, Kogi State to the North and part of Delta State to the east. The main ethnic groups in Edo State are Edos- the Bini speaking people of 18 Local Government Areas of the state (57.54%), Afemais comprising the Etsako (12.19%), Esans (17.14%), Owans (7.43%) and Akoko Edos (5.70%) (Abdul-Qadir, et. al., 2021). The land mass is about 19187 sq km suitable for oil palm production hence the choice state. Information that formed the data were collected using a well- structured questionnaire, personal observation and personal interview method. A multi-stage sampling technique was adopted for this study. The first stage was the selection of the three agricultural zones in the State for a complete representative of oil palm farmers in the State. The second stage was a purposive selection of twelve local government areas comprising 5 LGA from Edo South, 5 LGA from Edo Central and 2 LGA from Edo North that showed evidence of high oil palm farmers' concentration. The third stage was a purposive selection of 2 communities from Edo South and 1 community each from Edo Central and Edo North (10= ED S, 5=ED C, 2=ED N) and a random sample selection of 15 respondents from Edo South, 12 each Edo Central and 20 from Edo North giving a total of 250 respondents that were used for the analysis. This is clearly shown below:

Table 1: Sampled State by Agricultural Zones, Local Government Areas, Communities and Respondents

Parameters	ED S	ED C	ED N
Agric Zones	1	1	1
LGAs	5	5	2
Communities	2	1	1
Respondents	15	12	20
Total	1×5×2×15=150	1×5×1×12=60	1×2×1×20=40

Sum Total = 250

Source: Field Survey 2025

ED S = Edo South Agro Zone, ED C = Edo Central Agro Zone and ED N = Edo North Agro Zone

The Contingent Valuation Method (CVM) was adopted to illicit information from the farmers on how they will act if placed in certain contingent situation as it sets bidding prices and establishes if smallholder farmers will/will not pay for agroforestry based techniques at a particular price. The benefits of the agroforestry based techniques were elicited with price tag representing the value of agroforestry based technique. The information formed the data collected and was ranked using Likert Scale Model rating on a four point rating scale of; “Strongly Agreed, Fairly Agreed, Agreed and Disagreed” to get the values that formed the variables. Data were analyzed with descriptive statistics and probit model. Descriptive Statistics were obtained using frequencies and percentages for the socioeconomic characteristics and probit model that explains the yes/no decision by set of variables relating to smallholder characteristics agroforestry based techniques in relation to their bidding prices as they are willing or not willing to pay. The socioeconomic features analyzed were; age, sex, marital status, educational level, household size, experience, farm size, annual income etc were tableted in frequencies and percentages. The values from the likert scale rating which formed the explanatory variables as income (₦), soil erosion control (₦), firewood collection (frequency/year), source of land improvement (soil nutrient) (₦), source of food (₦), shade management (₦), tree logging (frequency/year), aesthetic /.recreational value (₦) were fitted into the Probit model for the analysis to determine the factors influencing the willingness to pay for agroforestry based techniques by smallholder oil palm farmers. Probit model was chosen because of its dichotomous nature and has been used by some notable authors to determine the factors influencing the willingness to pay for particular goods and services (Akinyemi, Ekpa, and Adetunji, 2014; Okere, et al., 2021; Okere, et al., 2022; Okere, et al., 2023).

The Probit model form is:

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_n X_n + \epsilon \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

Y = the yes/no response for the willingness to pay or not

α= intercept/constant

β₁ - β_n = Coefficients of the Variables

ε = Error Term

X₁ = Age (years)

X₂ = Sex (Male = 1 or female= 0)

X₃ = Marital Status (dummy= 1 or 0)

X₄ = Educational Level (No)

X₅ = Farming Experience (years)

X₆ = Farm Size (Ha)

X₇ = Household Size (No)

X_8 = Annual Income (Naira)

X_9 = soil erosion control (Naira/ year)

X_{10} = spacing/shading (meter)

X_{11} = source of land improvement (soil nutrient) (Naira/ year)

X_{12} = source of food (Naira/ year)

X_{13} = tree logging (frequency/year)

X_{14} = aesthetic /.recreational value (Naira/ year)

X_{15} = intercrops/ crop types (Nos)

Where Y is the yes/no response for the willingness to pay or not, α is the intercept, X_1 - X_n is a vector of independent variables (socioeconomic characteristics; age, sex, educational level, sex, experience, farm size, income, soil erosion control, spacing/shading, source of land improvement (soil nutrient), source of food, shade management, tree logging, aesthetic /.recreational value etc), β_1 - β_n are the coefficients and ϵ is the error term.

Results and Discussions:

Table 2: Socioeconomic Features of Smallholder oil palm Farmers

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Age:		
20 – 30	10	4
31 – 40	73	29.2
41 – 50	101	49.4
≥ 51	66	26.4
Total	250	100
Sex		
Male	100	40
Female	150	60
Total	250	100
Marital Status		
Single	10	4
Married	150	60
Separated	40	16
Divorced	50	20
Total	250	100
Educational Level:		
Non formal	100	40
Primary	104	41.6

Secondary	29	11.6
Tertiary	17	6.8
Total	250	100
Farming Experience (yrs)		
< 5	20	8.0
5 – 10	88	35.2
11 – 15	118	47.2
≥ 16	24	9.6
Total	250	100
Farm Size (ha)		
1-2	105	42.0
3-4	100	40
≥ 5	45	18
Total	250	100
HHSize		
1-3	60	24
4-6	100	40
≥ 6	90	36
Total	250	100
Annual income		
50000-100000	100	40
150000-200000	105	42.0
≥ 2500000	45	18
Total	250	100

Source: Field Survey 2025

The result from the table showed that 75.8% of the farmers were above 41 years of age with lesser strength to carry on their daily farming activities and adopt the latest agroforestry practices. This is in line with the findings of Tesfahun, (2014) that older people hardly adopt new technologies and unwilling to pay for the agroforestry system based techniques. The result from sex indicated that 60% were females who find it difficult to spend their money on agroforestry based techniques as women played a more active role in the practices, processing and marketing of oil palm produce (Rebecca, 2016) even being known as a patriarchal enterprise. This is in contrast with the findings of (Tefahun, 2014) that being a male will increase the probability of willingness to pay for the proposed package. The result further showed that 81.4 % had mostly primary education. There is a

high indication that majority of them are not literate enough to be convinced on the technical knowledge of the agroforestry system based techniques despite being in use a difficult task thereby not willing to pay for them. It showed that 82.4% of them had 10-15 years of experience yet were unable to pay for the agroforestry system based techniques as they were accustomed with their old system and unable to pay for extra knowledge. Farm size indicated that 82% of them plants between 1-4 hectares which is in the range of smallholder farmers but were unable to pay for the agroforestry system based techniques to increase output due to their inherent nature of the farming activities. The result showed that 76% had a household size above 4 persons. This shows that a reasonable number of family labour will be utilized if actively participated in the farming activities hence the reluctances to pay for the agroforestry system based techniques. The annual income indicated that 82% of them earned less than ₦200000 per annum with only 18% above ₦2500000 as compared to the estimated average annual output (income) of integrated smallholder oil palm farmers from 2.7 – 7.4 tons per hectare in Nigeria (Solidaridad, 2020) which they failed to pay for agroforestry system based techniques.

Table 3. Probit Results of the Determinants of the Willingness to Pay for Agroforestry Based Techniques by smallholder oil palm farmers

Variables	Coefficients	Std Error	Z-test	Sign
Constant	-6.2673	1.3731	-2.863	0.030
Age	-0.023*	0.002	-2.24	0.020
Sex	0.005	0.044	0.46	0.620
Marital Status	-0.106	0.030	-3.43	0.010
Educational Level	0.033***	0.026	1.703	0.011
Farming Experience	1.523**	0.041	2.74	0.002
Farm Size	-0.061*	0.013	-3.698	0.020
Household Size	-0.042*	0.002	-3.821	0.010
Annual Income	0.004*	0.001	19.147	0.020
Management Practices	0.035**	0.015	2.352	0.002
Crops Types	0.021*	0.021	10.320	0.030
Soil nutrient	0.574	0.032	0.726	0.234
Spacing /shading	0.974***	0.054	1.901	0.011
Source of food	0.653**	0.012	2,457	0.021
Tree logging	0.351*	0.032	3.329	0.031
Aesthetic	0.322**	0.053	2.841	0.022
Pearson Chi- Goodness Square – of – fit Test	13745.199 (P < 0.01)			

Pseudo R²

= 0.6848

***significant at 1% level, ** significance at 5% level and *significance at 10% level.

The Probit analysis showed that age of the farmers was negatively significant at 10% level indicating that any 1% increase in the age of the farmers leads to a proportional 2.24% decrease in the willingness to pay for the based techniques. This implies that the older the farmer the lesser the likelihood to pay for agroforestry system based technique as observed by Akinyemi, Ekpa and Adetunji, (2014). The result also reveals that farm size and household size each at 10% were negatively significant implying that a decrease in each of them leads to a 3.698 and 3.825 decrease in their likelihood to pay for based technique which is in contrast with the findings of Chandrasekaran, Devarajulu et al., (2009), that increase in farm size increases the willingness to pay for the system as enough output (yield of different crops) and family labour will be obtained (Mesa-Jurado, Martin-Ortega et al., 2012). Education had positive significant effect on willingness to pay at 1% level of significance. This showed that educated people are willing to pay for based technique than less educated people. This result is reasonable enough since being educated could be related to a better understanding of providing knowledge and makes the household get information as it creates awareness about the benefits obtained from improved increasing output through agroforestry based technique (Mezgebo, Tessema et al., 2013). This is consistent with the findings of Alao, & Shuaibu, (2013); Afroz et al (2009) and Chuen-Khee & Othman (2002) who observed similar studies in Bangladesh and Malaysia respectively. The result showed that annual income, crop types and logging of tree each at 10% played a significant role in the willingness to pay. This indicates that any 1% increase in annual income results to a 19.147%, 10.320%, and 3.329% respectively proportional willingness to pay for agroforestry based technique. It further showed that a smallholder oil palm farmer with higher value in the variables is likely to demand for agroforestry based technique and more willing to pay for it as observed by Balana, Catacutan et al., (2013) and Mbow, Van Noordwijk, Luedeling, Neufeldt, Minang & Kowero, (2014), who obtained similar results on household income that higher income households are more likely willing to pay a pre-specified initial bid than lower income households. It also suits the general demand theory which states the positive relationship between income and demand for goods. Management practices, Sources of food and Aesthetic were significant at 5% level indicating that any 1% increase in each of them leads to a proportional increase of 2.352%, 2.457% and 2.841% willingness to pay for agroforestry based technique as observed by Montagnini, Somarriba, Murgueitio, Fassola, & Eibl, (2015). This is in consonance with the findings of (Akinyemi, Ekpa, and Adetunji, 2014; Iiyama, Neufeldt, Dobie, Njenga, Ndegwa, & Jamnadass, 2014). The pseudo R² of 0.6848 or 68.48% variations of the included significant explanatory variables were accountable for by the smallholder oil palm farmers' willingness to pay for agroforestry based techniques hence should be upheld and encouraged to be practiced.

Conclusion:

The willingness to pay for the agroforestry based techniques by smallholder oil palm farmers is akin to the number of factors. The willingness to pay for a particular product is the likelihood to pay a certain amount for that in monetary terms. This was achieved in this study as a result of the socioeconomic features of the smallholder oil palm farmers, who indicated that a majority of them were in their middle/old age of 41 years, with more females (60%) and 81% mostly primary education, which affected their willingness to pay for the agroforestry based techniques. The Probit model result showed that higher educational level, farming experience, annual income, crop types, logging of trees, management practices, sources of food and aesthetic significantly influenced smallholder oil palm farmers' willingness to pay for improved agroforestry based techniques to improve output, enhance sustainability, improve soil practices and increase the living standard of the farmers. The study recommends and encourages the regular practice as it is another stream of income as oil palm monoculture is no longer enough for the teeming population in constant supply of food and raw materials, still improving the soil level; hence education and farming experience should be increased as well as income, which are the likelihood to pay for the agroforestry based techniques.

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